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People Without Health Care in Europe

The percentage of the population that does not have access to health care in Europe has decreased on average for the countries considered by 34% between 2008 and 2021

The Eurostat calculates the percentage of the population having an equal or higher age of 16 that do not have access to medical assistance for financial reasons, due to the presence of waiting lists and for issues related to the kilometer distance. The data are collected through self-selection and therefore reflect the value of the subjective perception of the interviewees and their socio-cultural background. However, the indicator does not take into consideration the differences between the various national health systems.

Ranking of European countries for the value of people who do not have access to health care in Europe. Estonia is in the first place for percentage of the population without access to health care for a value of 8.1%, followed by Greece with 6.4% and Slovenia with a value of 4.8%. In the middle of the standings there are Croatia with an amount of 1.7%, and Denmark and Sweden with an amount of 1.3%. Germany, Cyprus, and Malta close the ranking with an amount of 0.1%. On average in 2021 the value of people who do not have access to health care in the countries considered was 2.16%.

Ranking of European countries for the value of the percentage variation of the population without access to health care between 2008 and 2021. Slovenia is in first place for the value of the percentage variation of the population without access to health care between 2008 and 2021 with a value of 2,300.00% equal to 4.60 units, followed by Finland with an amount of 450.00% equal to an amount of 3.60 units and from Belgium with an amount of 240.00% equal to an amount of 1.20 units. In the middle of the standings there are Estonia with an amount of 10.96% equal to an amount of 0.80 units, followed by the Netherlands with an amount of -33.33% equal to an amount of -0.10 units, and Sweden with an amount of -50.00% equal to -1.30 units. Bulgaria closes the ranking with an amount of -93.46% equal to an amount of -14.30 units, followed by Germany with an amount of -95.45% equal to an amount of -2.10 units and from Cyprus With an amount of -96.43% equal to an amount of -2.70 units.

Clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the silhouette coefficient. Below is a clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the silhouette coefficient. Specifically, three different Clusters have been identified or:

- Cluster 1: Romania, Bulgaria, Latvia and Poland;
- Cluster 2: Switzerland, Czech Republic, Denmark, Luxembourg, Malta, Spain, Sweden, Netherlands, Germany, Austria, France, Belgium, Hungary, Slovenia, Portugal, Ireland, Lithuania, Cyprus, Finland;
- Cluster 3: Estonia, Greece.

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From the point of view of the median it is possible to identify the following structure of the Clusters or: $C3 = 7.25 > C1 = 3.35 > C2 = 1.1$. From a geographical point of view it is highlighted how southern Europe and some Eastern European countries have levels of access to lower health care compared to central-northern Europe levels.

Network analysis with the Euclidean distance. Below is a clusterization by applying the network analysis network with the Euclidean distance. The presence of a single complex network structure composed as below is detected or:

- Switzerland has a connection with the Czech Republic for an amount of 0.18 units;
- The Czech Republic has a connection with Switzerland for an amount of 0.18 units, with Luxembourg equal to an amount of 0.19 units, and with Spain for an amount of 0.24 units;
- Luxembourg has a connection with the Czech Republic for an amount of 0.19 units, with Spain for an amount of 0.14 units and with the Netherlands for an amount of 0.23 units;
- Spain has a connection with the Czech Republic for an amount of 0.24 units, with Luxembourg for an amount of 0.14 units, with the Netherlands for an amount of 0.16 units, and with Austria for an amount of 0.22 units;
- The Netherlands have a connection with Spain for an amount of 0.16 units, with Austria for an amount of 0.14 units and with Luxembourg for a value equal to 0.23 units.
- Austria has a connection with Spain for an amount of 0.22 units and with the Netherlands for an amount of 0.14 units.

Conclusions. Between 2008 and 2021 the value of the percentage of the population without access to health care has decreased by an amount of -34.46% equal to a value of -1.14 units. However, there are countries where this variable has grown or Slovenia, Finland, Belgium, and Spain. The growth of the population that does not have access to health care can be due to a set of factors or:

- Economic factors: in countries that have private or mixed health systems, it can be very difficult in conditions of economic crisis accessing care for the range of the population having low incomes;
- Geographical factors: for example in a country such as Greece, the resident population in the islands could have difficulties in having adequate access to treatments for geographical motivations;
- Lack of health services: in some countries having medium-low incomes there may be a difficulty in producing health services especially in rural areas and in internal areas by creating a subordination of services compared to the demand.

Certainly, the health issue in Europe, together with the issue of pensions, requires attention from policy makers. The European population is subjected to a widespread aging process with a growth of pro-capita health expenditure in an economic scenario that is very heterogeneous. If on the one hand, the countries and regions with high income show high levels also in health services, on the other hand, the countries and regions with medium-low per capita income could suffer even more in the future for deprivation in the 'access to health services. It is likely that the health inequalities between European countries and regions with medium-high and medium-low income will grow, creating differences also in the life expectancy. In fact, it is likely that the population that has more access to health care can also have a higher life expectancy than the population which instead is without access to medical treatment.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

